

Speculation on an Alternative Quantum Entropy Part II

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Sept. 26, 2022

In Part I we suggested that a free quantum particle with wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$ should have a spatial Shannon's entropy associated with the probability $\cos(px)/C1$ over half a wavelength, where $C1$ is a normalization constant. This new entropy captures the idea of uncertainty due to the wavelength even though the constant velocity suggests uniform motion i.e. $W^*(x)W(x) = \text{constant}$.

This idea was extended to a bound state and yields different results than the usual $P(x)=W^*(x)W(x)$ and $P(p) = a^*(p)a(p)$ based Shannon's entropies where $W(x)=\text{wavefunction} = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$.

In this note we try to determine some properties of this new entropy. First we consider the high n limit and use a classical approach introduced in (2). Next we expand the bound state entropy to include both spatial and momentum entropies and show that the sum follows from the product probability $|W(x)|/C1 \ |a(p)|/C2$ where $1/C1$ and $1/C2$ are normalization constants.

We also examine quantum adiabatic processes. For $P(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$ and $P(p)=a^*(p)a(p)$, one finds that such a process leads to S_p+S_x remaining unchanged for L changing adiabatically for a box with infinite potential walls or for k the spring constant changing adiabatically in an oscillator. This follows from the fact that $W(x/L)$ or $W(x \cdot 5\sqrt{k/m})$ (oscillator), from the normalizations $\int P(x)dx = 1$ and $\int P(p)dp = 1$ and from $\exp(ipx)$ which shows that p scales in reciprocal manner of x . Thus we argue that these properties still hold for the entropies defined using $|W(x)|$ and $|a(p)|$ as probabilities. In other words S_p+S_x for the new quantum entropy does not change under a quantum adiabatic transformation.

Finally we note that the new entropy is not compatible with the first law of thermodynamics.

Large N Limit

In (2) the high n (energy limit) of quantum spatial oscillator entropy (Shannon's entropy using $P(x)=W_n^*(x)W_n(x)$ where $W_n(x)$ is the oscillator wavefunction) is evaluated classically replacing $W^*(x)W(x)$ with the classical density $C/[v(x)v(x)]$ where $.5mv(x)v(x) + V(x) = E_n$. Here C is a normalization constant and $E_n = \hbar \omega (n+.5) = .5k AA$ where A is the classical amplitude. In (2) it is shown to be independent of n . To see this consider:

$B = \int dx \ C/v = 1$ with $v = \sqrt{2m(E-V(x))}$ and use $x=A \cos(\omega t)$ and $E=.5kAA$ Then

$1 = CC \int d(\cos(\omega t)) / \{ \sqrt{k} f(t) \}$ so AA disappears i.e. E disappears and there is no n dependence.

For $\int CC \ dx/v \ln(1/v)$ one has: $\int dt \ f(t)/\sqrt{k} \ln(kAA f^2(t))$ so the result is:

$B1 + B2 \ln(E_n) \rightarrow \ln(n)$ for n very large.

This same type of analysis may be applied to a Shannon's entropy using $|W(x)|$ as a probability. In such a case $\int C/v(x) dx = 1$ so C goes as $1/\sqrt{A}$. For entropy:

$$S_x \text{ new} = \int dx C/v \ln(C/v) \rightarrow \ln(1/A) \rightarrow \ln(1/\sqrt{E_n}) = -.5 \ln(E_n) \rightarrow -.5 \ln(n).$$

Product Probability

In previous notes we argued that the form $S_p + S_x$ may be obtained by using the probability $W(x)a(p)\exp(ipx)$ in Shannon's entropy. For the new quantum entropy based on $|W(x)|/C_1$ and $|a(p)|/C_2$ where $1/C_1$ and $1/C_2$ are normalization constants:

$$S = S_p + S_x \text{ follows from Shannon's entropy for: Probability} = |W(x)|/C_1 * |a(p)|/C_2$$

Quantum Adiabatic Processes

In a previous note (3) we considered that $S_p + S_x$ using $P(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$ and $P(p) = a^*(p)a(p)$ does not change under a quantum adiabatic transformation for a particle in a box with infinite walls or for an oscillator. This is due to three properties:

(1) And (2): $\int P(x)dx = 1$ and $\int P(p)dp = 1$ suggesting that the normalization constant of $P(x)$ goes as $1/L$ and for $P(p)$ as L for the box and as \sqrt{km} for $P(x)$ of the oscillator and as the reciprocal for $P(p)$ because of the form $\exp(ipx)$

(3) The wavefunction is a function of the adiabatic parameter i.e. $\sin(x/L)$ for the box and $\sqrt{km}x$ for the oscillator. Thus one may change variables and the normalization constants take care of dx or dp converting them to dy . The only issue is the $\ln\{\text{normalization constant} * \text{function}(y)\}$ which yields a term $\ln(\text{normalization constant})$. Given that x and p scale in the opposite manner because of the form $\exp(ipx)$, the x normalization constant and the p one are reciprocals so $\ln(a) + \ln(1/a) = 0$ and the adiabatic parameter disappears completely from $S_p + S_x$.

The new quantum wavefunction uses $|W(x)|$ and $|a(p)|$ as probabilities, but all of the properties above still hold. One needs just note that the normalization constant changes because it is no longer:

$$\int dx C \sin(x/L) \sin(x/L) = 1, \text{ but } \int dx C_1 |\sin(x/L)| = 1$$

C_1 thus goes as $1/L$. Given $\exp(ipx)$, one expects the normalization constant of p to go as L .

Similar arguments hold for the oscillator where $W_n(x) = C \exp(-\frac{1}{2} \sqrt{km} x) H_n(\sqrt{km} x)$.

CC goes as $1/(km)^{25}$ for $P(x)=W^*(x)W(x)$ so $S_x = \int dy \text{Function}(y) + \ln(\sqrt{1/\sqrt{mw}})$ where $w=\sqrt{k/m}$. For $P(p)=a^*(p)a(p)$ the normalization constant goes $C_p C_p$ goes as $(km)^{25}$, but $H_n(p/(km)^{25})$ and $S_p = \int dy \text{Function}(y) - \ln(\sqrt{1/\sqrt{mw}})$.

For the new entropy $|W(x)|$ has a normalization B which goes as CC and $S_x = \int \text{Function}(y) dy + \ln(B)$.

Thus it does not matter whether the probability is quadratic in $W(x)$ or linear (same for $a(p)$) because the normalization constant ensures that:

$S_x = S(\text{number with no parameters}) + \ln(\text{Normalization}(x))$ and

$S_p = S(\text{number with no parameters}) + \ln(\text{Normalization}(p))$ where

$\text{Normalization}(p) = 1/\text{Normalization}(x)$

Thus $S_x + S_p$ is free of parameters and does not change under quantum adiabatic transformations.

Adiabatic parameters such as L for the box and k,m (spring constant, mass) for the oscillator only appear in the normalization.

One may note that in classical statistical mechanics $-kT \ln(\text{Normalization constant})$ is free energy where:

$\text{Normalization} * \sum_i \exp(-e_i/T) = 1$.

Thus $\ln(\text{normalization})$ is a familiar form.

As a result, the new quantum Shannon's entropies based on probabilities $|W(x)|$ and $|a(p)|$ ensure that a quantum adiabatic transformation is also isentropic (just as the probabilities $W^*(x)W(x)$ and $a^*(p)a(p)$ do).

Classical Thermodynamics

This does not necessarily mean one may use the new entropies in the first law of thermodynamics. The new entropies are defined to capture the uncertainty of the wavelength of a free particle even though p means uniform "center of mass" motion with no uncertainty varying over x. Classically if a particle with momentum undergoes an impulse changing from p to p1, energy changes from $pp/2m$ to $p_1p_1/2m$ which should be equal to the work done. There is no consideration of entropy. With the new definition of entropy, the free particle entropy for p1 and p2 differs so it seems the first law of thermodynamics does not hold for these new entropies.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we consider some properties of a new Shannon's entropy using the probability $|W(x)|$ and also $|a(p)|$ where $W(x) = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$. We note that for n (the energy level) becoming very large, one may approximate $|W(x)|$ by $C/v(x)$ where C is a normalization constant. One may then perform a classical calculation as in (2) to find the large n entropy. For an oscillator it is again proportional to $\ln(n)$.

We also note that one may form the product probability $|W(x)|/C_1 |a(p)|/C_2$ where $1/C_1$ and $1/C_2$ are normalization constants and obtain (from Shannon's formula) $S = S_x + S_p$ with the new probabilities. We consider quantum adiabatic transformations for a particle in a box with infinite potential walls (changing L) and an oscillator changing k and find that like with the probabilities $W^*(x)W(x)$ and $a^*(p)a(p)$, the new probabilities also lead to an isentropic process when a quantum adiabatic transformation is performed.

Unlike the first law of thermodynamics, however, the new spatial entropy for a free particle suggests a different relationship because a free particle with p_1 may receive an impulse and change to p_2 . The change in kinetic energy equals work done, but the entropy is changed because p_1 and p_2 correspond to different wavelengths.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Particle_in_a_box
2. Majernick V and Opatiny Y. Entropic uncertainty in classical quantum Oscillator (J Phys A Math Gen, 1995, UK) <http://www.ktf.upol.cz/tom/clanky/jpa96-ent.pdf>
- And Ruggeri, Francesco R. Estimating Entropy of High Energy Single Particle Wavefunctions (preprint, zenodo, 2019)
3. Ruggeri, Francesco. R. Speculation on Quantum Thermodynamics and the Adiabatic Theorem(preprint, zenodo, 2022)